
The Impact of ICT In Library Automation

Dr. Vinod P. Masram

Shri Shivaji College of Physical Education, Amravati

Corresponding Author - Dr. Vinod P. Masram

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Abstract:

The automation technology improvement in the society, Library automation refers to the use of the computer to automate the typical procedures of libraries such as cataloging & circulation in the process of library automation, a library makes the use of computers & other technologies to support its systems & services.

Automation is a process of using machinery for easily working & saving human power & time. The main purpose of library automation is to free the librarians & library staff. Recent trends in library automation include the growing importance of digital content letter integration with the web environment for academic library.

Keyword: Automation, Barcode Reader, ICT, Institution Library.

Introduction:

Information has been always resources for creating material welfare in the human society. The computer and information technology has helped the library professionals to preserve these print & non print materials in a systematic & logical order.

The half of twentieth century with the advent of Information Technology, which was the converging technology of computers, communication, media & a host of other technologies?

Libraries are known for using information & communication Technology (ICT) both for automation of its routine activities as well as providing search services to the users computers are not only used as a data processing tool, but also for information storage, access & retrieval. Integrated library automation packages were introduced in libraries in 1970s. Minicomputers were used in

1970 s. in the libraries to computerize operations like circulation, acquisition, cataloging, serials & library OPAC. Computers are being used increasingly to automate various activities in libraries using a suitable off the shelf general or specific purpose software package now available in a wide range for library automation. This module covers definition, history, need & purpose of library automation planning for library automation i.e. Cataloging, OPAC, Circulation, Acquisition, Serials control etc. Barcode Technology & RFID is also covered in the module.

Information - What is Automation?

Information is the main source of development of the society, society cannot progress without the proper information centers. Preserve & give information to the new generations for research & development.

The term automation is introduced used first D.S. Harder in 1936. He defined it as, “The automation is handling of parts between progressive production processes. Since then the term has been applied to a wide variety of automatic Machinery and automatic systems. And is action for human efforts of intelligence.

Need for Library Automation:

It is also mandatory for any college for undergoing NAAC accreditation / re accreditation following are some points will clear that the need of library computerization. There are several reasons for automation a considerable saving in efforts. Time & resources involved in manual processing can be achieved the other reasons are

1. To use services of the existing staff effectively.
2. To improve control over collection.
3. To avoid duplicate of work.
4. To have an entries control over the entire operation.
5. To introduce new services as well as improve the existing services.
6. Save time of the users & Library Staff.
7. Give modern IT bases services to the users like OPAC and use of barcode technology.

Objectives of the Study:

1. Importance Staff Library Automation.
2. Advantages & Disadvantages of Library Automation.

Library Automation is Necessary because:

1. Bibliographic record is of variable length.
2. Updating of files is done almost every day.
3. To record the date accurately.

4. E-journals & e-Books easily available for students.
5. Easy Accessing in library software

Advantages of Library Automation

1. Easily searching of information.
2. Time saving.
3. Speedily communication.
4. Easily working with the help of Automation.
5. It motivate to library staff.
6. Helpful in stock verification.
7. Increased computer awareness among users.
8. Improved control covers library collection.
9. Increased computer awareness among users.
10. Excellent control over circulation.
11. Improved control covers library collection.
 - Some library Software
 - SOUL
 - e-granthalay
 - LIBSYS etc.

Library Automation & Networking

The library management software (LMS) Provide cataloguing, automated printing of catalogue cards & and also maintain the membership record.

The library provides online search service to its users. The online services are

- OPAC
- Online Journal
- N.List (Books & Journals)
- Internet Service
- CD- ROM Search

Disadvantages of Library Automation:

- It is long term & time-consuming process.
- Security Problems.
- It is totally depended on the electricity.
- Financial Expenses.
- Continuous staff training are required for it

Conclusion:

An Automated library can provide better library services to their users and can maintain the library more properly. The record keeping activity & various report generation becomes very easy in an automated library system.

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